

A Tutorial on Modeling Water Voids in Airborne LiDAR Point Cloud Data to Hydroflatten Water Surfaces in Digital Elevation Models.

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This tutorial is a more detailed step-by-step version of the one on the GRASS tutorials website, <https://grass-tutorials.osgeo.org/>, and is designed for new users to GRASS who are not familiar with the GRASS GUI interface.

In this tutorial, you will learn to:

- Create a mean ground raster data layer from LiDAR point cloud dataset.

- Install GRASS Addons to extend functionality.

- Add an OGC Standard Web Map Service (WMS) to the GRASS Map Display

- Create flat elevation data and edge standard deviation data raster layers for all areas of ground point voids in the LiDAR point cloud.

- Create 2D vector break lines and river center lines using the GRASS vector editor.

- Create automatic river transects

- Create hydroflattened river raster data for inclusion in a DEM

- Create a filled DEM layer combining the mean ground data, hydroflattened data, and other interpolated data.

- Export the resulting data from a GRASS project to a standard raster data format.

<https://grass.osgeo.org/grass-stable/manuals/addons/r.hydro.flatten.html>

Step 1: Set up GRASS

To create a raster surface from LiDAR point cloud data, current versions of GRASS must be compiled with the PDAL libraries, <https://pdal.io/en/stable/>. This capability is currently only available on Linux and OSX platforms. This capability will be available on Windows when GRASS switches to the cmake-based build system(currently in development).

On Windows, the pdal library is not currently compiled in the GRASS binaries. This issue currently being addressed in development. In the meantime, The meant ground raster surface needed for the hydroflattening portion of the tutorial can be created on Windows using the QGIS point cloud tools to a create virtual point cloud, https://docs.qgis.org/3.40/en/docs/user_manual/processing_algs/qgis/pointclouddatamanagement.html#build-virtual-point-cloud-vpc, and then export to raster (selecting classes 2,10,13 and setting the output resolution to 3.2808 ft), https://docs.qgis.org/3.40/en/docs/user_manual/processing_algs/qgis/

[pointcloudconversion.html](#) . See Appendix A at the end of the document for detailed directions.

On Linux

Ubuntu – based distributions:

1) Add UbuntuGIS unstable PPA,

<https://launchpad.net/~ubuntugis/+archive/ubuntu/ubuntugis-unstable> ,

2) install GRASS: `sudo apt install grass grass-gui grass-dev`

Fedora – based distributions : `sudo dnf install grass grass-gui`

Arch Linux distributions: `pacman -S grass`

Step 2: Acquire data:

Location: Lake Logan Near Hazelwood, NC

Upper Left WGS84 Coordinates 35.425931,-82.944451

Lower Right WGS84 Coordinates 35.406112,-82.911544

QL1 LiDAR data 2018 project. While you can go to the USGS GIS data download site at <https://www.usgs.gov/the-national-map-data-delivery/gis-data-download> and launch the National Map Data Download application and search for the data, the direct links to the individual data tiles are below.

Download links to the QL1 LiDAR data files used in this exercise to cover Logan Lake:

https://rockyweb.usgs.gov/vdelivery/Datasets/Staged/Elevation/LPC/Projects/NC_Phase5_2018_A18/NC_Phase5_Haywood_2017/LAZ/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00862212_laz
https://rockyweb.usgs.gov/vdelivery/Datasets/Staged/Elevation/LPC/Projects/NC_Phase5_2018_A18/NC_Phase5_Haywood_2017/LAZ/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00862320_laz
https://rockyweb.usgs.gov/vdelivery/Datasets/Staged/Elevation/LPC/Projects/NC_Phase5_2018_A18/NC_Phase5_Haywood_2017/LAZ/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00863205_laz
https://rockyweb.usgs.gov/vdelivery/Datasets/Staged/Elevation/LPC/Projects/NC_Phase5_2018_A18/NC_Phase5_Haywood_2017/LAZ/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00863209_laz
https://rockyweb.usgs.gov/vdelivery/Datasets/Staged/Elevation/LPC/Projects/NC_Phase5_2018_A18/NC_Phase5_Haywood_2017/LAZ/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00863317_laz
https://rockyweb.usgs.gov/vdelivery/Datasets/Staged/Elevation/LPC/Projects/NC_Phase5_2018_A18/NC_Phase5_Haywood_2017/LAZ/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00862208_laz

Step 2: convert point cloud data to 1m mean ground raster

1) Create a text file with a list of .laz files with the full directory name. (i.e, ls /home/dnewcomb/lidardata/*.laz > laslist.txt)

the content of the laslist.txt file will look like this:

```
/home/username/sample_lidar/lake_logan/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00862212_laz  
/home/username/sample_lidar/lake_logan/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00862320_laz  
/home/username/sample_lidar/lake_logan/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00863205_laz  
/home/username/sample_lidar/lake_logan/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00863209_laz  
/home/username/sample_lidar/lake_logan/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00863317_laz
```

/home/username/sample_lidar/lake_logan/USGS_LPC_NC_Phase5_2018_A18_LA_37_00862208_.laz

2) Start GRASS – If this is the first time you have opened GRASS you will see the default startup screen with a WGS84 world project. Click on the Create new project button in blue on the left.

3) The LiDAR data is in the EPSG:6543, North Carolina State Plane Feet NAD 83(2011) Coordinate Reference System (CRS). In the Define new GRASS Project dialog, enter nc6543 as the name of the project and click next.

4) In the Select Coordinate Reference System(CRS) dialog, stay with the default Select CRS

from a list by EPSG or description and click Next.

5) In the Select CRS from List dialog, type 6543 in the Filter by EPSG Code or Description search box. This will narrow the selection to the NAD83(2011)/North Carolina(ft US) option and highlight it in blue. Click Next.

6) A small Select datum transformation dialog box will pop up with a default of 1 selected in blue. Click OK.

7) The project Summary dialog will pop up, showing you the projection definitions for the project. Click Finish.

Your Main GRASS interface will now look like this:

The next step is to import the ground point data from the 6 industry standard .laz format LiDAR data tiles to create a seamless mean ground elevation layer at 1m resolution. The data is in NC State Plane Feet, so we will be using a conversion factor of 3.28084 to convert the Feet to Meters for the resolution.

Fortunately, the GRASS command `r.in.pdal` automates several aspects of this process. Click on File→ Import Raster Data→ Point cloud (LAS LiDAR) import (`r.in.pdal`).

This will bring up the r.in.pdal dialog.

The r.in.pdal dialog has multiple tabs that allow for several parameters for processing the point cloud data into a 2D raster.

Starting with the Input Tab, the first option is to choose an individual LAS, or LAZ (including COPC) file for processing.

Alternatively, for processing multiple files , the second option is to select a text file that lists the names of the files to process and the location of the files in the file system. You will use the second option for multiple files for this exercise.

Browse to and Select the laslist.txt file created in Step 2 for the second text box as input.

Click on the Output tab on the top of the dialog window. Check the boxes for:

- Use the extent of the input for the raster extent, and
- Set computation region to match the new raster map.

Type in lake_logan_1m for the Name for the output raster map.

Type in 3.28084 for the Output raster resolution. (While the project is in survey feet, and the LiDAR data is in survey feet, the desired cell size is 1 meter, so put in the conversion factor mentioned above.)

Click on the Statistic Tab at the top of the dialog

Note -----
 GRASS needs to have an extent set to match the extent of the data and a resolution (raster cell size) set to create a raster data set matching the data. So long as there is CRS data in the LiDAR data set that GRASS recognizes, the extent and resolution of the project can be automatically set in this tab. If GRASS does not recognize the CRS, the extent and resolution of the project work area must be set manually using g.region.

Keep the default Statistic to use for raster values as mean. This means that for the LiDAR points that fall in each cell, the mean Z value of the points will be calculated and set as the cell value.

Click on the Selection tab in the Dialog window.
Scroll down to :
[Multiple] Only import points of selected classes.
Type 2,10,13 in the text box

Class 2 is the official ASPRS
(https://www.asprs.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/07/LAS_1_4_r15.pdf) standard classification for ground points.

At the time this data was collected, Class 10 was commonly used to designate ground points that were within 1 meter of 3D break lines for water bodies (newer data sets use Class 20) , and were withheld from use for ground model construction using the TIN method. The State of North Carolina contracted to have the points that represented roads to be Class 13. So, to get the complete ground point data set, selection of Classes 2,10,and 13 is required to use all of the ground points.

Click on the projection tab at the top of the dialog window.

Check the box for Reproject to project's coordinate system if needed.

This option allows you to create a raster from data that may not be in the exact same projection (CRS) as your GRASS project. In this case, the data is in the same projection, but the projection is labeled slightly differently. Once again, this only works if the CRS is recognized by GRASS.

Note-----

Sometimes the CRS data is missing in the LiDAR data set, or the CRS information is in a format that is incompatible with what GRASS reads. If that is the case, the option is to manually set the CRS, resolution, and extent of the GRASS project to match the data, and then check the box for Override projection check (use current project's CRS)

Click on the Optional tab at the top of the dialog window.

Check the box for Allow output files to overwrite existing files. Make sure the Add created map(s) into layer tree is checked near the bottom.

Since this is training, you may try this more than once before you get the correct results. If the output dataset name is the same, GRASS will stop the command with an error. By default GRASS will not let you overwrite an existing dataset. Checking the overwrite box allows the process to overwrite an existing data file.

You will also note the Add created map(s) into layer tree box near the bottom is checked by default. This will automatically place the results in the Layer panel and display them in the Map Display.

You may have noticed a line of text growing across the bottom of the dialog window as different options are filled in. All analysis in GRASS can be run from text input in the Terminal window that starts with the GRASS Graphical User interface, or in the Console tab of the lower right portion of the User interface

If you click on the Copy button near the bottom of the r.in.pdal dialog window

This will copy the text version of the command to the clipboard of the operating system, that you can then paste to your favorite text editor. Pressing the Copy button and then pasting produces the this text version of the command. This is useful if you need to rerun the command from the text prompt, from the Console tab in the panel on the right side of the GUI, or you wish to automate the process via the python interface.

```
r.in.pdal -w -e -n --overwrite output=lake_logan_1m  
file=/home/username/sample_lidar/lake_logan/laslist.txt resolution=3.28084  
class_filter=2,10,13
```

Click on Run.

The tab will automatically switch to the Command output tab and will give results of the analysis in text form when finished.

If you have followed these instructions, you will see the [lake_logan_1m@PERMANENT](#) layer listed in Layers panel in the lower left, but you will not see the data. While the analysis was done at the location of the data, the view in the Map Display panel did not switch to the location of the data.

Right click on the lake_logan_1m layer and the select Zoom to selected layer(s) option

The view in the Map Display panel will switch to the extent of the created raster layer.

The elevations indicated in the mean ground height layer vary from blue (low) to yellow (high) . The red line around the perimeter indicates the computation extent.

To show the range of values graphically , add a legend by selecting the Add map elements icon on the top bar.

Then select Add raster legend.

This brings up the d.legend dialog. The default settings with lake_logan_1m selected as the raster layer will work for this example. Click OK

Map Display 1 now shows a basic raster legend with the range of elevations in Survey Feet NVD88 for the data.

For more details, right click on the lake_logan_1m layer in the Layers panel and select the bottom option for Metadata.

The panel on the right side of the GUI will switch to the Console tab and display the text metadata for the lake_logan_1m layer from the r.info command. You will need to grab the left edge of the panel with your mouse and drag it to the center to see the full text.

Besides getting the number of cells, CRS information, and extent, The Minimum and Maximum values are displayed. The complete command string which generated the raster layer is also saved with the Metadata.

You see the nodata areas for the lake and river, but what are the other nodata areas? You can pull up the 6 inch ortho photo data via a Web Map Service (WMS) image service using the add WMS layer button in the Layers panel.

This will bring up the Add web service layer dialog

The State of North Carolina has a program to collect aerial imagery on a 4 year cycle. These data sets are provided as both ESRI image services and OGC standard WMS services. The most current data set for this location is from 2023. The URL to access the WMS data set is https://services.gis.nc.gov/secure/services/Imagery/Orthoimagery_2023/ImageServer/WMServer .

Data is also available for 2019, 2015, and 2010 for this area, just substitute those years for 2023 in the URL above if you wish to review those years.

Once the URL is copied and pasted into the Server settings text box,click on the Connect button.

Click on the triangle just below to Show advanced settings.

In the Layer Manager Settings section , you will see Orthoimagery (2023) automatically populated.

Available web services should list WMS 1.3.0. In the Request tab under Available web services, you will see Orthoimagery (2023) listed with a triangle to the left.

Click on the triangle and you will see Orthoimagery(2023) listed below. Click on the (2023)Orthoimagery option.

There are multiple options for Source projection in the dropdown below this defaults to EPSG:4326, but you will want to match the CRS of your project to optimize responsiveness, so select EPSG:6543. Also select the jpeg radio button in the Source image format.

Click Add layer. Your GUI should now have Orthoimagery (2023) listed as one of the layers in the Layer panel, and the imagery will be drawn in the Map Display.

It is recommended to click on the Save button on the top of the Add web

service layer dialog and enter a descriptive name to quickly recall the image service between sessions.

The Orthoimagery layer can be slow to load. To save time, uncheck the Orthoimagery(2023) layer and zoom into one of the void areas to the left of the lake. Once you have zoomed in , check the Orthoimagery(2023) layer and see what the void represents.

Step 3: Installing the r.hydro.flatten Addon to GRASS and modeling water surfaces.

GRASS Addons are installed in the GUI by using the Settings drop-down at the top and selecting Addons extensions → Install extensions from addons [g.extension]

This will open the Fetch & install extensions from Grass Addons dialog. Click on the triangle next to the raster option to reveal the raster addons available.

Scroll down in the raster section and select r.hydro.flatten

You will notice that installation messages will appear in the console tab on the right side.

```
(Sun Jun 15 06:51:25 2025) Command finished (0 sec)
(Sun Jun 15 06:57:55 2025)
g.extension extension=r.hydro.flatten
WARNING: Extension <r.hydro.flatten> already installed. Re-installing...
Fetching <r.hydro.flatten> from <https://github.com/OSGeo/grass-addons/> (be patient
Already on 'grass8'
Compiling...
Your branch is up to date with 'origin/grass8'.
Installing...
Updating extensions metadata file...
Updating extension modules metadata file...
Installation of <r.hydro.flatten> successfully finished
(Sun Jun 15 06:58:02 2025) Command finished (6 sec)
```

Including download time, installation took 6 seconds.

At this point, you could run `r.hydro.flatten` from the command line, (typing `r.hydro.flatten` and enter), but it would be easier going forward if the command was integrated into the Tools tab. Restarting GRASS will automatically load the `r.hydro.flatten` tool in the Addons portion of the Tools tab.

Click on the File dropdown menu at the upper left of the GUI and select Quit. The Quit confirmation dialog will come up

Click on Quit GRASS GIS . The store current settings dialog will then pop up .

Select No.

Start GRASS again. You should now see an Addons option in the Tools tab. Click on the triangle next to it and you will see r.hydro.flatten listed in the Addons

Double Click on r.hydro.flatten. This will open the r.hydro.flatten dialog. The Required tab opens by default.

Select lake_logan_1m for the Raster map of binned lidar elevation.
Type in lake_logan_1m_wat_elev for the Raster map of derived water elevation.
Type in lake_logan_1m_wat_stddev. for the Raster map of the derived standard deviation
Replace 5 in Percentile of elevation to determine water level with 14. (per data presented at the North Carolina GIS Conference, March 20, 2025, recording on YouTube, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5L21o7IubIA&t=2s&pp=0gcJCckJAYcqIYzv>)

Click on the Optional tab. Check the box for Keep intermediate results.

Click Run. The dialog will switch automatically to the Command output tab and display the steps the r.hydro.flatten program is going through to calculate the estimated elevations of the voids from the 14th percentile of the edge values of each void in the ground point data and the standard deviation of the edge values around each void.

On the main GRASS GUI, click on the second icon from the left in the Data panel (Reload current GRASS mapset only). This will refresh the view of datasets in the (current) PERMANENT mapset.

Once the refresh is finished, you will see all of the intermediate layers used to create the Water Elevation and Standard Deviation raster layers.

The way that `r.hydro.flatten` works is that it takes the mean ground elevation layer and interpolates 3 cell3 into each void to fill in the small holes (`intermediate_rfillstats`). Then with the remaining voids, the voids are converted to a raster layer (`intermediate_reclass` for clump) and used as a base to buffer back out (`intermediate_buffer`) to capture the strip of cells that represent the original edge of the void (`intermediate_strip`).

The buffer is again used to create a raster layer that covers each remaining void and the strip around the void. These areas are processed to have a unique integer value for each contiguous clump of cells (`intermediate_clump`). The clumped rasters are used as zones to compute zonal statistics on each strip in the `intermediate_strip` layer. The standard deviation and the requested percentile value (14) are calculated and saved internally to a text file with the unique ID. The unique IDs are used to reclassify the values of the clumped areas to elevation and standard deviation raster layers for the void areas.

Uncheck the lake_logan_1m layer in the layers panel and double-click on the lake_logan_1m_wat_elev layer in the data panel. You should see just the water elevation layer in the Map Display panel.

Click on the 4th icon from the left at the top of the Map Display panel. This is the Query raster/vector tool. When this tool is active, it will return the value(s) of single or multiple selected layers.

Click on the lake in the center of the view.

A Query results dialog will open with the results of the value of the raster layer at that location. The value of the raster is 2855.316 feet NVD88.

Now click on the smaller body of water just to the Southeast of the main lake.

You will notice that the elevation of this pond is 2912.684 Feet NVD88. Since these two bodies of water are separated by a road on an embankment, it is unlikely that there is a 57 ft elevation difference between them.

Double click on the lake_logan_wat_stddev layer in the Data panel. This layer represents the standard deviation value of the edges of each water body. The default color style is a ramp from white (0.11) to bright red (32.46).

As you can see, the pond has such a low value that it is almost white. The river upstream of the main lake (southwest), the lake, and the river downstream of the lake (northeast) all seem to have the same color. Click on the lake_logan_wat_elev layer to select it, and then use the Query tool to find the elevation of the river above the lake, in the lake, and the river below the dam. You will find that they are all at 2855.316 Feet NVD88.

The reason for this is that the statistics for the edge of the water are what determines the calculation of the elevation of the water. The river flows into the lake without interruption and the water is flowing over the dam, so the calculation is done on the edges of the lake and river (upstream and downstream) as a single unit.

The calculation needs to be interrupted at the dam and the point the river flows into the lake to give an accurate elevation estimate of the water level. This is done by creating a vector layer and drawing 2D break lines at locations that define the boundaries of the lake.

Turn off the display of the lake_logan_1m elevation and standard deviation layers by unchecking the boxes on the left of layers in the layer panel. Leave the mean ground layer displayed.

Go to the Vector drop-down at the top of the GUI. Select Develop vector map → Create new vector map

This will bring up the Create new vector map dialog. Type in logan_2D_break.

Click OK. The new vector layer will appear in the Layers panel.

Note: GRASS raster and vector names must always start with a letter, and not a number.

Right click on the vector layer you just created in the layers panel, and select Start editing.

This will open the vector digitizer toolbar in the GRASS GUI just below the Map Display Toolbar.

Zoom in to the north side of lake logan where you see the semicircle of the dam, and click on the add line tool in the toolbar.

With the Digitize new line tool activated, left click to digitize a line across the the gap in the mean ground raster layer.

For very thin areas like this dam, it's best to draw the line all of the way to the bank on both sides. Right click after the last point to finish the line. You should see a Define attributes dialog after ending each line. Click submit to finish the line.

Use the pan tool on the top tool bar to move to the Southwest portion of the lake where the river comes into the lake. Draw another line across the river where it enters the lake. Don't try to get the end of the line right on the edge of the river, make sure it is fully across on both sides.

Click on the icon on the far right to stop digitizing ,

The Save changes dialog will open.

Click on Yes

Re-run the r.hydro.flatten tool and change the output water elevation and output standard deviation layers by adding _2dbreak to the previous names.

On the Optional tab, uncheck keep intermediate results and use the dropdown for Name of input vector map to select logan_2dbreak.

Click Run.

Recheck the elevations between the lake and the small pond . There is now less than 3 feet of difference in the elevations.

If you check the standard deviations of the lake and the upstream and downstream rivers, you will find that the standard deviation of the lake is now less than 3 feet. The upstream river has a standard deviation of 18.137 feet and downstream river has a standard deviation of 9.96 feet.

The river sections are being modeled , like the lake, as single flat segments, while the standard deviation of the edges indicate that they sections of the river modeled are not flat.

To fix this issue, you can break up a river into smaller sections of flat segments by adding 2D break lines across the river at regular intervals.

One could manually digitize all of the crossing lines across the rivers, but that is time consuming and does not ensure regular spacing. Another alternative is to draw or use existing center lines for the river and automatically create evenly spaced transects across the river using the v.transects addon,

<https://grass.osgeo.org/grass-stable/manuals/addons/v.transects.html>

Install the v.transects using Settings→ addons extensions → Install extensions from addons, in the same way you installed r.hydro.flatten. You will need to close GRASS and restart for v.transects to appear in the Tools tab.

Once you have restarted GRASS, add lake_logan_1m from the Data panel to the Layers panel. Create a new vector layer called centerlines. Then draw center lines for the river above and below the lake.

The center line does not have to be perfect . For longer river areas, the Intermediate_strip raster layer could be converted to a vector layer and used as input for the v.centerline addon. <https://grass.osgeo.org/grass-stable/manuals/addons/v.centerline.html>. For many rivers, national hydrologic datasets like the USGS NHD data may already have centerlines available for use. Drawing them manually is sufficient for this exercise.

Once the centerlines are drawn and saved, click on the Tools tab at the bottom right of the GUI , click on the triangle next to the Addons category, and double click on the v.transects [v.transects] option

This will open the v.transects dialog. For Name of input vector map use the centerlines layer you created. For Name of output vector map, type in centerlines_120_trans . As you might guess, the Transect spacing along input polyline is 120.

In the Optional tab:

- Check the box at the top for Use the last point of the line to create transect.

- Set Distance transects extends to the left of the line to 60

- Set Distance line extends to the right side of the line to 60 .

- Set Input feature type to line.

- Set Determines how transect spacing is measured to along, so the spacing follows the curve of the line you digitized.

- Set Determines which line is the transect perpendicular line to line, so the transect is perpendicular to the line you drew and not the general direction of the line.

Once the output transect layer is added to the Layers panel you will see the transects generated on the Map Display. You will note that some of the transects do not exactly line up with the shoreline correctly.

Right click on the transect vector layer and select start editing to bring up the vector editing toolbar. Select the move selected vertex tool and use it to select and move the ends of the line to line up correctly. (Left click to select, left click to select new location, right click to complete move.)

Exit and save from editing mode.

Since r.hydro.flatten only takes one vector layer input for the 2D vectors, you will need to either merge the dam and upstream lake break lines from the previous section into the transect layer , or edit the transect layer and redraw those lines.

You should edit the transect layer where the river enters and exits the data set. Putting a final line across the void area prevents r.hydro.flatten from going around the corner and analyzing outside edge pixels as part of the shoreline data of the last segment of the river.

Zoom back into the Dam and turn on the Orthoimagery 2023 layer. The lines of the centerlines transect layer are hard to see, so right click on that layer and select Properties.

Once the d.vect dialog opens, click on the Colors tab. Click on the Feature Color section. This opens the Choose color dialog. Select the yellow box in the Palette section in the middle of the bottom of the dialog. Click Select. The Choose dialog will close. Click on the Apply button in the d.vect dialog. Then click Close.

In the orthophoto, you can see the dam line at the top of the dam. The first transect is placed at approximately the downstream edge of the plunge pool below the dam. It's probably a good idea to put a break line at the base of the dam as well.

Turn on the mean ground layer and place it above the Orthophoto layer in the Layers panel. The Orthophoto was taken 5 years after the LiDAR data was collected, so it is unlikely the water levels will exactly match. Digitize the line along where you see the dam structure meet the water and save it. While you are editing the vector layer, the lines will turn black for the layer you are editing. Once you save your edits, the line color will revert to yellow.

Rerun `r.hydro.flatten`. This time, use `centerlines_60` as your input vector layer and `lake_logan_1m_filled_DEM` for Raster map representing filled digital elevation model.

The resulting filled DEM looks like this:

From a distance, this looks very smooth. Turn off the DEM layer and display the vector cross sections standard deviation layer and add a raster legend for the standard deviation layer.

You will see the the lake and river are very light, indicating that the edge values for the lake and most of the river sections have relatively low standard deviation values. There is a red spot in the top center of the study area.

Zoom into the northeast corner to view that area, the dam , and the rest of the river. Use the Query tool to see value of the bright red area.

This area has a standard deviation value of 32.46 ft , indicating a large range in the edge values. By comparison, the lake has a standard deviation value of 2.89 ft.

If you look at the area on the orthoimagery, you see dense evergreen vegetation. This is an area with a substantial void in the ground points that is not water.

This areas can be mitigated by converting all areas above a given standard deviation value to NULL, then filling the resulting NULL areas with r.fillnulls.

Re-run r.hydro.flatten , changing the output layer to lake_logan_1m_filled_DEM_null_above_5_stddev and setting 5 for the Maximum value of standard deviation to fill the DEM section.

The result will look like this:

In the Raster → Interpolate Surfaces section, select r.fillnulls

This will bring up the r.fillnulls dialog. Set the input layer to [lake_logan_1m_filled_DEM_null_above_5_stddev@test3](#) , the output layer to lake_logan_1m_filled_DEM_final . Leave the rest to the defaults and click Run.

This will fail on hole 3. Hole 3 is one of the high standard deviation NULL areas along the edge for which the RST algorithm cannot find enough edge points to interpolate. (See <https://grass.osgeo.org/grass-stable/manuals/r.fillnulls.html>) .

This can happen in areas where there are gaps in the raster data inside the computational boundary along the edge of existing data. The hydroflattening method will include values along the edge for any data voids that open to the edge.

One remedy to this issue is to create a boundary polygon covers the area just inside the area where the raster data becomes ragged.

This boundary vector layer can then be used by r.mask to create a mask layer that prevents interpolation along the outside edges for voids that open to the edge. Go to Raster→ Mask [r.mask] and in the Vector tab, select the vector polygon layer you just created.

Click Run.

This will remove edge irregularities from the analysis.

Re-run `r.hydro.flatten` with the mask, then re-run `r.fillnulls` on the masked layer. While there are several warnings, `r.fillnulls` finishes successfully to complete the DEM.

Alternatively, you can change to the bicubic interpolation method, which uses the bicubic b-spline method from `v.surf.bspline`, <https://grass.osgeo.org/grass-stable/manuals/v.surf.bspline.html>, to fill the NULL areas, but the edge values will be based on limited data and have lower confidence.

Step 4: Export to GeoTiff

The last step is to export the filled DEM to the open standard geotiff file format.

Right click on the `r.fill.nulls` filled DEM layer and select Export. This will bring up the `r.out.gdal` dialogue

Click on the browse button next to the Name for output raster file option to browse to the directory where you want the geotiff file to be written. Keep the default file format as Gtiff (Geotiff).

Click on the creation tab. On this tab you can select the Data type and compression level for the output image. From the Data type drop-down select Float64.

Once the Data type is selected, go to the [multiple] Creation option(s) to pass to the output format driver section. The different options for writing out a geotiff raster can be found at the GDAL Gtiff format description page, <https://gdal.org/en/latest/drivers/raster/ztiff.html>

Type in compress=deflate,predictor=3 .

Click Run. The dialog will automatically shift to the Command output tab and you will see a message similar to this:

```
r.out.gdal input=dem_holes_fillnulls@PERMANENT
output=/home/username/sample_lidar/lake_logan/lake_logan_1m_filled_dem_final.tif
format=GTiff type=Float64 createopt=compress=deflate,predictor=3
Checking GDAL data type and nodata value...
Using GDAL data type <Float64>
Exporting raster data to GTiff format...
ERROR 6: lake_logan_1m_filled_dem_final.tif, band 1:
SetColorTable() only supported for Byte or UInt16 bands in
TIFF format.
r.out.gdal complete. File
</home/username/sample_lidar/lake_logan/lake_logan_1m_filled_dem_final.tif> created.
```

Deflate compression is the most recognized lossless compression for geotiffs by other software and is relatively fast for reads. The predictor option allows the deflate compression to be more efficient. You can leave the geotiff uncompressed, but the file size will be about 4 times larger than the deflate compressed version. This difference adds up as you scale this process up to larger data sets.

 Note: For Geotiffs larger than 4GB, you will need to use the BIGTIFF=YES option to successfully write an output raster. You may want to also add the num_threads=4 to enable the multi-threaded writing option as well.

Appendix A: Using QGIS on Windows to Create a Mean Ground Raster Layer

Step 1 : Create virtual point cloud and build mean ground raster

Open QGIS

Start> QGIS 3.40.X>QGIS Desktop 3.40.X

This will open the QGIS Desktop application:

In the browser panel, scroll down to the XYZ tiles and click on the triangle to show the layers underneath. Select the OpenStreetMap tiles and drag it to the map canvas.

This will open the global OpenStreetMap data set in the map canvas (copyright OpenStreetMap contributors).

Step 1: Create Virtual Point Cloud (VPC)

If not already open, open the processing toolbox panel (Processing>Toolbox)

In the Processing Toolbox go to the Point cloud data management section, select Build virtual point cloud(VPC)

This will bring up the Build virtual point cloud dialogue. Click on the input layers button.

Click on the Add Files button and use the standard windows dialogue to navigate to the directory where the 6 .laz files were downloaded and select them. Click on the triangle at the upper left of the dialogue to get back to the main dialogue.

Click on the button to the right of the Virtual point cloud box and select Save file.

Browse to the directory where the target .laz files are, and give a descriptive file name like lakeloganvirtual and select the file type as vpc.

Click Save and then the Run button at the bottom of the dialogue.

The virtual point cloud layer may come in with a question mark next to it. This means that QGIS does not know the projection of the VPC index file.

Right click on the VPC layer and select Layer CRS>SetCRS

This brings up the Coordinate Reference System dialogue. In the Filter text box, type in 4326 . Select EPSG:4326-WGS84 from the window below and select OK. This will set the Coordinate Reference System for the VPC to EPSG:4326 , commonly known as WGS84.

Right click on the lakeloganvirtual layer and select zoom to layer. Your canvas should now look like this.

At this point, we need to set the project CRS to match the LiDAR data, which is EPSG:6543 , North Carolina State Plane Feet NAD83/2011.

Click on the EPSG:4326 window at the bottom right of the main QGIS window. This will bring up a similar CRS dialogue for Project Properties. Enter 6543 in the filter text box, and select NAD83(2011) /North Carolina(ftUS). Click Ok

The text in the lower right corner should now read EPSG:6543. This may seem a bit weird, but while the LAZ data tiles are in EPSG:6543, the VPC index layer is in EPSG:4326.

Click on the paintbrush in the upper left corner of the Layers panel

This opens the style panel on the right side of the QGIS window. Since the VPC layer is selected, it shows the current display style for the virtual point cloud layer. Near the top of this panel is a paint brush. Next to the paint brush is a drop down menu which is currently set on classification. Click on the drop-down menu and select Extent Only.

You will now see the extent of the 6 LiDAR point cloud tiles referenced by the VPC file.

Now that the VPC file has been created, a 1m resolution mean ground elevation layer needs to be created.

Click on the Processing toolbox tab at the lower right of the QGIS window to access the Processing Toolbox commands. Click on the triangle next to point cloud conversion to see the conversion options, then double click on Export to raster.

This will bring up the Export to raster dialog. Make sure the input layer is the lakeoganvirtual.vpc layer. Keep the Attribute as Z. Set the Resolution of the density raster to 3.28084 (the number of feet in a meter) Leave the Tile size for parallel runs at 1000.

Click on the triangle next to Advanced Parameters click on the button next to the Filter expression[optional] box to open the Filter Expression dialogue. In the Attributes box, double click on Classification then click on the IN operator. In the parenthesis for the In operator, type in 2,10,13. These values correspond to the ground, ground withheld near breaklines, and road surface classes in this data set

Click Ok to accept the filter settings. Click on the button next to the Exported Text Box and select Save to File.

Browse to the directory where you want the mean ground Geotiff file to be created and give it the name lake_logan_1m.tif

Click Run at the bottom of the dialog. This will take a few minutes to complete, then you will see the results on the canvas. The default is a grayscale image of the elevation values where there are ground points. The NULL areas are where the water surfaces or other gaps in the ground points occur.

Save the project
Close QGIS

Step 2 : Link raster to GRASS

Start GRASS GIS . If you installed QGIS using the Standalone Installer, GRASS GIS is available under the QGIS application folder as well.

The GRASS GUI interface will look like the Linux version. In the Data panel in the upper left, click on the first globe icon on the left to create a new project.

Follow the instructions in the Linux section above to create a GRASS project with the CRS for EPSG:6543 .

After creating the project, click on File>Link external data>Link external raster data.

This will bring up the Link external raster data dialogue. In the dialogue, browse to the location of the mean ground geotiff file you just created and select it. The mean ground geotiff will be listed in the table in the middle and by default the name of the layer in GRASS will be the same as the filename without the .tif suffix. Click Link.

In the Console panel on the right, you will see when the link command is completed. The linked raster will show up in the Layers panel on the left. Close the Link external raster data dialogue.

You will see nothing in the Map Display Window. While you have successfully linked the data to GRASS, no colors have been assigned to the data layer. To make the data visible, right click on the lake_logan_1m layer and select the Set color table option.

This will bring up the Set Color Table dialogue. Select the Define tab at the top and use the Drop down menu for the Name of the color table to select the elevation option. Click Run.

When the command has finished, you will see the mean ground data in the Map Display.

Right click on the lake_logan_1m layer and select Set computational region from selected map.

The tutorial can now be continued above from the point after the r.in.pdal section.